

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MUSIC PSYCHOLOGY IN PERFECT HUMAN EDUCATION

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Musical psychology is one of the scientific directions that studies the influence of music on the human soul and the direct analysis of the psychological component in the architecture of musical works. For example, two people can hear the same music in the same way, but they perceive it in completely different ways. The study and deep analysis of such aspects is the reflection of music psychology.

Among the main areas of music psychology, there are many branches of science. This is the psychology of musical feelings, the psychology of musical hearing and the psychology of musical abilities. In addition, it comprehensively examines the factors (social, genetic and psychological) that influence musical creativity, the acquisition and development of exceptional musical abilities, and non-standard musical thinking.

Music affects the basic structures of our soul, but in some cases this effect can be positive, on the contrary - it can be very negative. The main task of the psychology of music is to convey the melodies heard under the influence of musical works to the listener at the level of perfection. In today's world, this direction is widely used in advertising and business, in particular, there is music that encourages people to buy more or to perform their duties effectively at work. Although the mechanism by which such "mood music" affects the human mind is not yet fully understood, experts in the field of music psychology continue to develop in this field.

Human life is divided into two parts: the surrounding life and the unique world of the human heart. Each of us thinks, imagines and dreams, and evolves in parallel with humanity. Music rounds out our thoughts and directs them in a direction that takes positivity, playfulness, rudeness or aggressiveness. For centuries, people can determine their character and inner world by looking at what kind of music they like. At first, it was possible to determine the environment in which a person lives by understanding musical styles and playing foreign and national compositions. Now, based on what music a person prefers, it is possible to determine his conversational circle, his lifestyle and interests, and clearly divide people into subcultures.

The healing properties of music not only bring a person out of depression, but also relieve physical pain. Self-healing is more important than any medicine, and it is

what each of us hopes for in difficult situations. Uplifting music inspires people to live, rejoice and believe in goodness and shines light into the world.

Music always moves in parallel with our memories. Of course, not every person has songs related to his childhood memories. For example, Moses, the son of the great pharaoh Ramses, heard music from his childhood and remembered his true origin. Have you ever felt this way? Undoubtedly, yes. All of us have had a moment when we heard a song from our childhood and remembered in detail our happy and carefree times. Music is a powerful associative factor, because once we hear a song, we remember it for a lifetime, and we know approximately how it will continue the next time we hear it. We can't get such a strong effect even from speed, when we encounter a picture, there is a strong suspicion that the next time we face it, it will look different to us.

Stendhal, the great French literary scholar, said: "Perfect music moves the soul in such a way that you feel this feeling as if you were enjoying a beloved creature, that is, music, without words, bestows the brightest happiness in the world." .

In fact, he gave a very accurate description of good music. Someone may agree with this, and someone may not, but one thing is certain: Music makes a person live and move. Music is the source of life, the source of creativity, the food of the soul, the mirror of the nation. Music culture is a concrete force that spiritually cleanses the members of the society, grows their hearts, gives strength to the inner world and will of a person, awakens the national conscience, and is in constant motion.

The future and tomorrow of independent Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without young people. The art of music has a direct and strong influence on a person from his youth and occupies a great place in his general cultural development. Music, which occupies a wider place in the cultural life of a democratic society, is a constant companion of a person throughout his life. Music is the only art that penetrates deeply into the human heart and has the power to vividly express this soul.

Music - aesthetic education, must become a component of the great work being carried out on the path of harmonious education of a person of a democratic society. Musical work with children is especially important. Music evokes a strong psychological and emotional feeling in a child's heart.

It is impossible to educate children with rich physical, spiritual and strict moral qualities without developing musical perception in children. The art and education of music develops human qualities in a person, calls for spiritual purification and elevation, enriches the inner world of a person, strengthens faith,

will, and awakens creativity. provides. With the help of music, his artistic perception grows and his emotions become richer.

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